

A PILOT CLINICAL STUDY ON THE EFFICACY OF AN HERBAL FORMULATION CONTAINING *CURCUMA LONGA*, *PIPER NIGRUM*, AND *COCOS NUCIFERA* IN SUPPORTING COLORECTAL HEALTH AND PREVENTING EARLY BOWEL ABNORMALITIES.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Chronic gastrointestinal (GI) inflammation, driven by pathways such as NF- κ B and STAT3, plays a pivotal role in the pathogenesis of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) and its progression to colorectal cancer (CRC). This study evaluated the therapeutic rationale and preliminary clinical outcomes of a novel nutraceutical formulation comprising *Curcuma longa* extract, *Piper nigrum* extract, and *Cocos nucifera* oil. **Methods:** The formulation was designed to target inflammation, oxidative stress, mucosal integrity, and gut microbiota balance through complementary mechanisms. A Phase I pilot study assessed tolerability and symptomatic improvements in patients with irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) and mild IBD. **Results:** Curcumin exhibited anti-inflammatory effects via NF- κ B inhibition and COX-2 suppression, while piperine enhanced curcumin bioavailability and modulated TLR-4 signalling. *Cocos nucifera* oil provided mucosal protection and facilitated phytochemical absorption. In the pilot study, 70% of participants achieved complete resolution of major GI symptoms, with the remainder showing moderate or mild benefit. Rapid improvements were noted in abdominal pain, bowel irregularities, constipation, and bloating. Age-stratified analysis suggested faster pain relief in younger adults and greater bowel regularity improvements in older adults. No dropouts or adverse events occurred. **Conclusions:** Preliminary findings indicate that this multi-targeted nutraceutical is safe, well-tolerated, and potentially effective for symptom relief in functional and low-grade inflammatory GI disorders, with implications for CRC prevention. Larger randomized controlled trials with biomarker and microbiome analyses are warranted to validate efficacy, optimize dosing, and assess long-term benefits.

KEYWORDS: Curcuma longa, Piper nigrum, Cocos nucifera, Inflammatory bowel disease, Gut microbiota, Colorectal cancer prevention, Nutraceutical formulation.

INTRODUCTION

A key pathological condition that affects the digestive system is chronic inflammation as observed in inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), which includes Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC). The inflammatory environment is characterized by elevated levels of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (ROS/RNS) and pro-inflammatory cytokines.^[1,2] When such a milieu persists, its DNA damage, genomic

instability, and the accumulation of mutations that can ultimately lead to the development of colorectal cancer (CRC).^[3] In addition to inflammation, other factors such as gut microbiota imbalances, immune dysregulation, genetic susceptibility, and environmental exposures are also implicated in the pathogenesis of CRC.^[4] Furthermore, epidemiological evidence supports a link between chronic inflammatory bowel diseases and CRC, with ulcerative colitis-associated cancer most commonly

affecting the rectum and sigmoid colon, whereas in Crohn's disease, cancer occurrence is more diffusely distributed across various segments of the colon.^[1] In a diseased condition like ulcerative colitis (UC) progressive epithelial damage is triggered by a robust immune response. This response results in the infiltration of immune cells, excessive inflammation, and further tissue destruction, leading to a breakdown of normal colonic architecture. A key feature in UC pathogenesis is the overexpression of signal transducer and activator of transcription 3 (STAT3) and interleukin-17 (IL-17), both of which contribute to the chronic inflammatory state observed in the disease. STAT3, through its activation, promotes immune cell survival and cytokine production, while IL-17, produced by Th17 cells, drives the recruitment of neutrophils and exacerbates epithelial injury.^[5,2] In addition to these immunological factors, genetics and diet also play critical roles in the onset and progression of the disease. Several gene mutations especially those involved in immune regulation have been linked to increased susceptibility to ulcerative colitis (UC). Notably, germline mutations in DNA mismatch repair genes such as MLH1, MSH2, MSH6, and PMS2 have been implicated.^[6] Interleukin-6 (IL-6), a pleiotropic cytokine primarily produced by immune and epithelial cells, plays a central role in regulating inflammation, immune responses, and tissue homeostasis. In pathological conditions such as IBD and CRC, persistent or dysregulated IL-6 signalling contributes to chronic inflammation, tumour progression, and immune dysfunction.^[7] Similarly, IL-6 and IL-23 have been implicated in both the induction and maintenance of gut inflammation, a key contributor to colitis-associated colorectal cancer (CRC). The activation of nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B), a transcription factor central to the inflammatory response, has been shown to promote colon tumour growth in experimental models, particularly through its activity in intestinal epithelial cells.^[8]

In the case of Crohn's Disease (CD), immune cells such as CD4+ and CD8+ T cells, B cells, monocytes, and natural killer (NK) cells play a key role in the inflammatory response particularly in response to luminal bacterial infections.^[9] Intestinal barrier dysfunction in Crohn's Disease arises primarily from defects in the epithelial barrier, leading to increased intestinal permeability, decreased expression of defensins, and increased bacterial adherence. This dysfunction facilitates the activation of both innate and adaptive immune responses, particularly due to the failure to eliminate harmful bacteria, which subsequently triggers immune reactions. As a result, not only are pathogenic bacteria targeted, but the healthy gut microbiome can also be affected. Th1 cytokines produced by lamina propria lymphocytes play a significant role in this process, with their increased expression being driven by IL-12, IL-23, and TNF-like cytokine 1A (TL1A) from antigen-presenting cells.

This response is further amplified by B-cell reactivity to luminal microbes, further contributing to the pathogenesis of Crohn's Disease.^[10,11]

A condition that is under-studied would be thromboembolism (TE), a recognized extraintestinal complication of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), affecting both Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC). Although its prevalence has been inadequately investigated, recent case reports and screenings have highlighted its occurrence.^[12,13]

A study conducted between May 2021 and September 2023 recorded 302 outpatient visits among 23 patients with TE. Of these, 11 had venous thromboembolism (VTE) 6 with UC and 5 with CD. Twelve patients experienced arterial thrombosis, including five with Crohn's disease (CD) and seven with ulcerative colitis (UC). This distribution reflects the known cardiovascular risk patterns and underscores the importance of evaluating additional immunological and haematological contributors such as primary sclerosing cholangitis (PSC), which is strongly associated with UC in the ongoing monitoring of patients with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). Although the overall incidence of thromboembolic events (TE) remains low, heightened clinical vigilance is warranted due to the elevated risk in the Hungarian cohort.^[14,15] Hence it is necessary to take preventive measures considering the recent trends in their dietary pattern characterized by frequent consumption of smoked meats, high amounts of sugars and refined flour, alongside limited intake of fish, raw vegetables, and fruits.^[16] This is because dietary factors like high-fat or low-fibre diet, can disrupt the gut microbiota, further contributing to disease development and severity. In a multivariate analysis by Giovannucci.^[17] an association between red meat consumption specifically beef, pork, and lamb and an increased risk of colon cancer, particularly in the distal colon. The study found that processed meats such as bacon and hamburgers were positively associated with colon cancer risk when taken in higher amounts. However, consumption of red meat in forms such as hot dogs, sandwiches, or as part of a balanced vegetable dish showed no significant correlation with cancer risk. Notably, the study categorized participants into two subgroups: smokers and non-smokers. Interestingly, it concluded that individuals who began consuming red meat at an early age and were non-smokers showed increased susceptibility to colon cancer.^[17]

Environmental factors such as high dosing on antibiotics over time, Western-style diets, and cigarette smoking are also considered to be major contributors to the pathogenesis of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). Although the relationship between smoking and IBD remains complex, it has been observed that smokers have an increased risk of developing Crohn's disease (CD) and a decreased incidence of ulcerative colitis (UC), though the exact mechanisms remain unclear.^[18] This

paradox may be linked to the underlying etiology of these diseases. Haem and nitrosyl haem, primarily found in red and processed meats, have been identified as significant contributors to colorectal cancer (CRC) development. Their carcinogenic effects are thought to operate through three primary mechanisms: (a) increased N-nitrosation, (b) elevated oxidative stress leading to the formation of DNA adducts such as benzo(a)pyrene-DNA adducts (B(a)P-DNA), and (c) lipid peroxidation within the intestinal epithelium.^[19] Additionally, haem and other food-derived metabolites may induce proliferative stimulation of the epithelium either directly or after metabolic conversion. Chronic inflammation, driven by the overexpression of inflammatory mediators, further contributes to cancer risk by promoting site-specific mutagenesis and ultimately malignant transformation.^[20] Cross-contamination of processed or slaughtered red

meat, especially from cattle, can harbour pathogenic organisms including bacteria, viruses, and parasites that may have adverse health effects, particularly on the GI tract. In the same way, Consumption of raw meat and inadequately purified or contaminated drinking water can lead to parasitic infections that affect the gastrointestinal (GI) tract. These infections may compromise the integrity of the intestinal epithelium, causing symptoms such as abdominal pain, chronic or bloody diarrhea, ulcerative colitis, strictures, and potentially inflammatory polyps. Immunocompetent individuals who are subjected to immunosuppressant treatments are at an increased risk of contracting parasitic infections.^[21,22] *Entamoeba histolytica*, an invasive colonic pathogen, commonly causes mild abdominal pain and loose stools, often mimicking ulcerative colitis (UC).^[22]

Figure 1: Pathophysiological Links Between Chronic Inflammation, IBD, and Colorectal Cancer

Another example would be Enterohemorrhagic *Escherichia coli* (EHEC) that can produce attaching and effacing lesions on the mucosal lining of the distal ileum and colon. This leads to adhesion with enterocytes part of the gut microbiome and alters their expression.^[23] Although the role of parasites in the development of Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS) remains unconfirmed, it continues to be actively investigated. The contribution of parasitic infections to inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD) such as UC and Crohn's disease (CD) remains underrecognized.^[24] While certain parasites particularly helminths have been shown to alleviate IBD by suppressing pro-inflammatory cytokines and increasing anti-inflammatory cytokine levels, many parasitic pathogens such as *E. histolytica*, *Toxoplasma gondii*, *Trichinella* spp., *Microsporidia*, *Dientamoeba fragilis*, and *Blastocystis* spp. have been implicated as potential etiologic agents in the development of IBS, CD, and UC.^[25,26,27,28]

On considering the environmental stressors or fluctuations in intrinsic cellular maintenance systems can lead to alterations in the epigenotype defined as the

pattern of chemical modifications that regulate gene activity without altering the DNA sequence itself. These epigenetic changes, including DNA methylation, histone modification, and non-coding RNA regulation, have been associated with both environmental and lifestyle factors, and may play a significant role in modulating intestinal health and disease.^[29,30]

Genetic Influences on IBD and the Emerging Role of Nutrigenomics

Since the mapping of the human genome in 2003, our understanding of how genetic variation influences disease has advanced, giving rise to fields like nutrigenomics and nutrigenetics. These disciplines explore how diet interacts with genes to affect health and are especially relevant in conditions like inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), where genetics, nutrition, and environment intersect. Recent studies show that disruptions in the gene–diet–microbiota relationship can drive gut inflammation and increase long-term IBD-related cancer risk. As a result, nutrigenomics is being explored to develop personalized nutrition strategies to restore gut balance and reduce inflammation. A key

example in this area is Crohn's disease, a chronic inflammatory bowel condition with a well-established genetic component. One of the most strongly associated genes with Crohn's disease is NOD2 (nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain-containing protein 2). Specific NOD2 variants, including R702W, G908R, and 1007fs, have been linked to a significantly increased risk of developing the condition. These mutations may result from inherited predispositions, but their expression and impact are modulated by environmental influences such as diet, smoking, and gut microbial exposures.^[31] However, the presence of these NOD2 variants alone is not sufficient for a diagnosis of Crohn's disease. The condition is multifactorial, driven by a complex interplay of genetic susceptibility, environmental triggers, and immune dysregulation. Similarly, a combination of genetic and environmental factors is believed to contribute to the development of other inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD), such as ulcerative colitis.^[29] A study by Vetrano.^[32] demonstrated that deletion of the D6 decoy receptor significantly increases tumor formation in inflammation-associated colon cancer by impairing inflammation resolution through disrupted chemokine regulation.^[32] Alkylating DNA damage, especially in the distal colon where most colorectal cancers develop, is linked to dietary exposures such as processed red meat and associated with activating mutations in KRAS and PIK3CA; tumors with these mutations show higher levels of alkylation damage.^[33,34,35] These findings underscore the potential of genetically informed personalized nutrition to manage or prevent IBD. Furthermore, bioactive compounds may modulate gene expression epigenetically, as supported by a Phase I open-label human pilot study evaluating a formulated nutraceutical.

Key components involved in the nutraceutical formulation

Curcuma longa

Curcumin, the primary bioactive compound in turmeric, has long been recognized in India for its medicinal, culinary, cosmetic and spiritual significance. According to the *Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India* (API) *Curcuma longa* extract has been traditionally used for Visavikara, Kustha, Vrana, Tvagroga, Prameha and Pandu.^[36,37,38] In medical applications, curcumin and its curcuminoid derivatives from turmeric exhibit anti-inflammatory properties by suppressing the NF- κ B pathway, which regulates pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6, COX-2, and TNF- α . They also inhibit the arachidonic acid (ARA) pathway, which is involved in the production of reactive lipid mediators like eicosanoids. Due to turmeric's numerous benefits especially its anti-inflammatory, anti-parasitic, anti-bacterial, antioxidant, and anti-cancer properties many *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies have been conducted.^[39,40,41,42] One such study examined turmeric's effects on colon histology of mice and related conditions, while also assessing IL-23, Myeloperoxidase (MPO), and glutathione, which are key elements involved in immune signaling, immune

defense, and cellular protection, respectively. The study demonstrated a significant increase in serum glutathione levels, along with reduced levels of colonic myeloperoxidase (MPO) and interleukin-23 (IL-23), following oral administration of *Curcuma longa* (CL) extract. These findings suggest that CL has a protective role in the prevention of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). Furthermore, its administration after IBD onset may help mitigate intestinal barrier disruption and reduce the risk of complications such as colorectal cancer by suppressing chronic inflammation and limiting the development of inflammation-driven mutational changes in the colon.^[43] One of its notable pharmacological effects is the inhibition of Cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), an enzyme involved in inflammation and pain. COX-2 is also known to play a significant role in colon carcinogenesis, with overexpression observed in approximately 80% of colorectal cancer (CRC) cases. According to Goel *et al.* curcumin exhibits chemo preventive properties by selectively inhibiting the mRNA and protein expression of COX-2 at therapeutic concentrations, without affecting COX-1 expression [44]. Curcumin exerts its anti-cancer effects by modulating various immune mediators, including cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), reactive oxygen species (ROS), and cytokines, thereby helping to regulate inflammation and immune responses.^[45] Furthermore, Turmeric extract, particularly its active component curcumin, exhibits significant therapeutic potential through various mechanisms, including upregulation of P3 expression, improvement in body mass index (BMI), and modulation of the gut microbiome. Additionally, its anti-platelet activity may help counteract thromboembolism.^[46] By alleviating dysbiosis and promoting microbial homeostasis, curcumin could play a critical role in preventing complications associated with gastrointestinal dysbiosis, further supporting its role as a promising adjunct in health and disease management.^[47,48]

Piper nigrum

Piper nigrum, commonly known as black pepper, has a long history of medicinal use, particularly in the field of Ayurvedic medicine. The therapeutic applications of black pepper date back to ancient texts, where it was revered not only as a spice but also as a potent medicine for a variety of ailments. Historical references to the use of *Piper nigrum* can be found in texts such as the Charaka Samhita and Sushruta Samhita, which are two of the foundational works of Ayurvedic medicine. These ancient texts underscore black pepper's role in various therapeutic formulations, highlighting its use for digestive disorders and respiratory ailments. In contemporary Ayurvedic practice, as outlined in the *Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India* (API), black pepper is recognized for its therapeutic benefits in managing conditions like Svasa (asthma), Sula (pain), Krmiroga (intestinal worms), and Tvagroga (skin disorders). Given its diverse therapeutic properties, black pepper has gained attention in the treatment of Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS), where it is considered to assist in

digestive regulation, reduce inflammation, and support overall gut health.^[49,50,51,52, 53]

Piper nigrum has demonstrated multiple therapeutic effects, including its ameliorative action on ulcerative colitis (UC). Gupta et al. investigated the anti-inflammatory mechanisms underlying this effect, focusing specifically on the role of piperine in modulating Toll-like receptor (TLR)-mediated inflammation in the colon. Their study revealed that piperine significantly attenuated mucosal damage while suppressing levels of myeloperoxidase (MPO) and malondialdehyde (MDA), indicators of oxidative stress and lipid peroxidation. The TLR pathway is known to regulate inflammatory gene expression in colonic tissues, with TLR4 interacting with free fatty acids (FFAs) to initiate inflammation through downstream mediators such as NF- κ B and JNK, which contribute to chronic inflammation. In an acetic acid-induced mouse model that closely mimics human UC, administration of piperine notably reduced FFA levels, thereby alleviating inflammation.^[54] In a related context, the effect of piperine has also been studied in colorectal cancer, a condition often associated with mutations in the APC gene. These mutations inhibit the canonical Wnt signaling pathway, resulting in the overexpression of β -catenin, which drives tumor progression. Piperine has been shown to suppress this overexpression, thereby modulating Wnt signaling and potentially exerting anti-cancer effects.^[55] Several studies have formulated turmeric's bioactive compound curcumin together with black pepper's piperine, demonstrating enhanced effects in alleviating inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) and colon cancer.^[56,57,58] Based on these findings, we can hypothesize that piperine may enhance the therapeutic efficacy of curcumin through a positive synergistic interaction when used in combination.

Cocos nucifera

Natural coconut oil has a rich source of medium-chain saturated fatty acids (MCFAs), with lauric acid, a 12-carbon fatty acid being its predominant component^[59] In traditional Ayurvedic medicine, *Cocos nucifera* has been employed for its therapeutic properties in managing conditions such as Daha (burning sensation), Raktapitta (Bleeding disorders), and Trsna (thirst). Sosa, and Sula, as noted in the *Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India*.^[60] The triglycerides derived from coconut oil have found widespread application across various sectors, particularly the pharmaceutical industry, where they are utilized by scientists and researchers for their functional properties. Coconut oil has been used in households for generations, becoming a regular feature of people's daily lives particularly in Sri Lanka and other Asian Countries particularly due to its hypocholesterolemic, anti-hepatosteatotic, anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, antioxidant, chemoprotective, skin moisturizing abilities and anti-parasitic activity.^[61,28] Furthermore, a study conducted by Reddy et al. highlighted the significant role of dietary fat composition, particularly

fatty acids, in influencing colon carcinogenesis.^[62] Coconut oil has been shown to reduce inflammation and colon carcinogenesis in DSS-induced mice by decreasing TNF- α levels, which play a key role in colitis. Its consumption has also been shown to restore intestinal epithelial cell types such as goblet cells, the submucosa, and the crypts of Lieberkuhn.^[59] Another study by Zundler et al. reported a case of severe, refractory diversion colitis in a patient who had previously received extensive therapy with Hydrocortisone, 6-Mercaptopurine, Vedolizumab, Ustekinumab, and Infliximab, without clinical improvement. As surgical intervention via proctectomy was declined, an alternative treatment using coconut oil was initiated. Over a six-month period, the patient demonstrated marked clinical improvement, with reductions in rectal bleeding, haematochezia, mucus secretion, and inflammatory symptoms.^[63] Another study reported a possible increase in the levels of *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*, a beneficial gut microbe known for its role in improving conditions such as IBD and IBS, in mice fed a high-fat diet supplemented with coconut oil.^[64] Taken together, the available studies and case reports suggest that coconut oil, particularly through its rich content of medium-chain fatty acids (MCFAs), may offer broad-spectrum health benefits including support for cardiovascular, bone, and skin health, as well as neuroprotective effects. Most notably, emerging evidence points to its promising therapeutic potential in the management and alleviation of inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD), positioning coconut oil as a compelling adjunct in the dietary approach to chronic gut inflammation.

The combination of *Curcuma longa* extract, *Piper nigrum*, and *Cocos nucifera* oil targets key inflammatory and oxidative pathways implicated in gastrointestinal disorders. Curcumin's anti-inflammatory and anti-carcinogenic properties are enhanced by piperine-mediated bioavailability, while coconut oil contributes to mucosal protection and may suppress carcinogenic triggers. Together, this nutraceutical blend offers a functional relief in conditions such as dyspepsia and IBS, support mucosal healing in ulcerative colitis and gastritis, and potentially contribute to reduced risk of gastrointestinal malignancies. This article presents preliminary observations from a one-month Phase I pilot study involving ten patients, exploring the combination's safety and tolerability as a complementary approach for managing IBS and IBD. While limited by sample size and the absence of extensive biochemical data, the study observed subjective improvements in gastrointestinal symptoms, suggesting potential therapeutic value worthy of further investigation in larger, controlled trials.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Clinical Validation of a Nutraceutical Capsule Study Design and Ethical Approval

This study was a prospective, Phase I, open-label, single-centre, community-based pilot clinical study designed to evaluate the efficacy of a nutraceutical tablet composed

of *Curcuma longa* and *Piper nigrum* extracts, along with *Cocos nucifera* oil. The trial was conducted under the supervision of the Contract Research Organization (CRO), Ashram Siddha Research Institute. The study protocol (Protocol Number: LF-101-04-24) was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee for Clinical Research of the CRO, as constituted under Rule 7 and registered under Rule 8 of the Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO), operating under the Directorate General of Health Services, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. The study complied with the ethical guidelines for biomedical research on human participants as per the 2006 AYUSH-ICMR guidelines. In accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrolment, and they were thoroughly briefed on the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits.

Study Population

The trial was conducted in the city Salem, Tamil Nadu, India, where the estimated prevalence rates of Kroorakashta (Bowel Disturbances), Chronic Constipation presenting symptoms like Epigastric pain, pain in the lower abdomen, bloating of abdomen etc., exceeds 30% of the local population. The study was conducted over a 30-day period, from April 8, 2024, to May 7, 2024. Participants were recruited through an open-label, non-randomized, community-based process. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were determined based on comprehensive clinical examinations and reviews of medical histories. A total of ten participants, aged 20 to 60 years and presenting with the specified clinical symptoms, were enrolled in the trial. Individuals above 60 years of age or those with a history of osteoarthritis, drug or alcohol abuse, night or shift work, diabetic complications, psoriatic arthritis, or endocrine disorders were excluded from the study. Additionally, participants were withdrawn from the trial if their symptoms worsened or if they developed any serious condition requiring urgent medical attention.

Intervention

The investigational product administered in this study was a nutraceutical tablet containing a standardized blend of turmeric and black pepper extracts along with

coconut oil. Each tablet was formulated with 95% curcumin extract from *Curcuma longa* (Turmeric), 95% piperine from *Piper nigrum* and 99.9% pure virgin coconut (*Cocos nucifera*) oil. Participants were instructed to take one to two tablets orally, twice daily in the morning and evening, with lukewarm water, for the duration of the study. In addition to the daily tablet supplement, all participants received lifestyle counselling that included personalized dietary recommendations, physical activity guidance, and general health education to support therapeutic outcomes and encourage self-management of their condition. Compliance monitoring was conducted on patients to ensure adherence, participants were instructed to complete weekly adherence diaries to record daily intake.

Clinical Assessment and Evaluation

Comprehensive clinical evaluations were conducted on Day 1 (baseline) and Day 30 (end of study) by qualified Siddha and Ayurveda practitioners. Detailed case records were maintained for each participant throughout the study. Diagnostic assessments were carried out in accordance with traditional Siddha diagnostic protocols which involves the eightfold diagnostic method Envagai Thaervu, Tridosha Naadi a pulse diagnosis to assess the balance of Vata, Pitta, and Kapha, and Saptha Dhatu Thaervu meaning evaluation of the seven body tissues. These assessments provided a holistic understanding of the participants' health status and were used to monitor progress during the study. The primary outcome measure was defined as a minimum 10% reduction in presenting symptoms, as reported by the participants and confirmed by the clinical judgment of the attending physicians. This reduction was considered a clinically significant indicator of therapeutic success. Participants received detailed information about the study, including potential side effects, expected benefits, the right to withdraw at any time, and procedures for follow-up and referral, all communicated in their native language to ensure complete understanding. As depicted in Figure 2, the study cohort consisted of 6 males and 4 females, while 7 patients were aged 21-44 years and 3 patients aged 45-60 years. The efficacy of the nutraceutical supplement was evaluated over a one-month period by monitoring improvements in symptoms.

Figure 2: Age Group Distribution of Patients.

RESULTS

The present observational study consisted of a total of 10 participants, stratified into two age groups to understand the demographic distribution. Of these, 70% (n=7) belonged to the 21–44-year age group, while the remaining 30% (n=3) were in the 45–60-years of age category. This distribution reflects a predominance of younger individuals seeking treatment for gastrointestinal symptoms, potentially indicating either a higher prevalence or greater health-seeking behaviour among this population subset. Over the course of the 30-day intervention, participants reported marked

improvements in key gastrointestinal symptoms such as epigastric pain, lower abdominal discomfort, bowel irregularities, constipation, and abdominal bloating symptoms frequently seen in clinical presentations of IBS and, to a lesser extent, in milder forms or remission phases of IBD as per table 1. In the 21–44 age group, all six patients (100%) showed resolution of epigastric and lower abdominal pain by day 15, with sustained relief at day 30. In the 45–60 age group, four patients initially reported improvement at day 15, while three maintained symptomatic relief at day 30, indicating a 75% response rate.

Table 1: One-Month Improvement in Gastrointestinal Symptoms Following Intervention.

Age Group	Improvement in symptoms of epigastric and lower abdominal pain		% of Improvement	Improved bowel function (Kroorakoshta) and Chronic Constipation		% of Improvement	Improved bloating condition		% of Improvement
	15 days	30 Days		15 days	30 Days		15 days	30 Days	
21-44	6	6	100	4	3	75	4	3	75
45-60	4	3	75	6	5	83	6	5	84

Improvement in bowel disturbances such as altered frequency and consistency consistent with “Kroorakoshta” or functional constipation was observed across age groups. Among younger participants, 75% maintained improvement by day 30, while the older age group demonstrated a slightly higher response rate of 83%. A similar trend was noted in abdominal bloating, with 75% improvement in the younger group and 84% in the older group by the end of the intervention period. These findings suggest that the efficacy of the

intervention may be influenced not only by physiological factors but also by environmental and lifestyle aspects. Older individuals often live in more stable environments with lower exposure to stressors such as erratic work schedules, high screen time, and irregular meals common among younger participants. In addition, they tend to follow a more regulated and controlled diet, which may contribute to better digestive regulation and treatment responsiveness.

% of Improvement based on Age Distribution

Figure 3: Efficacy of a Nutraceutical Formulation in GI Symptom Relief Across Age Groups (or) Percentage improvement in gastrointestinal symptoms across two age groups (21–44 years and 45–60 years) following 15 and 30 days of nutraceutical supplementation.

In Ayurvedic terms, Kroorakoshta refers to a hard bowel type, characterized by infrequent or difficult bowel movements that often require stronger interventions to stimulate elimination. Interestingly, in older adults, despite the natural predominance of Vata dosha (which

can aggravate dryness and constipation), symptom relief is often more sustained. This may be due to the cumulative effect of disciplined eating habits, reduced metabolic demand, and consistent daily routines all of which support the body's response to Ayurvedic

treatments aimed at regulating koshta function. The figure 3 presents age-specific symptom improvement among participants experiencing mild gastrointestinal complaints associated with early-stage inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) and irritable bowel syndrome (IBS). The nutraceutical formulation was administered for 15 and 30 days. Outcomes assessed include improvements in epigastric discomfort, bowel function, and bloating. Orange bars represent the 21–44 age group, and green bars represent the 45–60 age group. Both age groups showed substantial symptom relief, with complete resolution of the symptoms listed in the both the cohort.

Cumulatively, analysis of all reported symptoms indicated that 70% of patients (n=7) experienced very good clinical improvement, characterized by the resolution of all four major symptoms. One patient (10%) showed moderate improvement in two to three symptoms, while two patients (20%) reported mild improvement,

involving partial relief in fewer than two symptoms. There were no cases of non-response or dropout, suggesting both clinical efficacy and good patient adherence to the supplement. The figure 6 depicts the chart illustrating the distribution of clinical symptom improvement in patients following one month of supplementation with the nutraceutical formulation. Clinical outcomes were categorized into five groups: Very Good Improvement (all 4 symptoms improved), Moderate Improvement (2– 3 symptoms), Mild Improvement (less than 2 symptoms), No Significant Relief, and Dropout. The green bars represent the number of patients in each category, while the orange line indicates the corresponding percentage. A majority of patients (70%) experienced very good improvement, while a small proportion showed mild or moderate improvement. There was no patient drop outs recorded, and no patients had reported a lack of significant relief.

Figure 4: Overall Clinical Symptom Reduction After One-Month Nutraceutical Supplementation.

The findings of this study indicate that the investigated nutraceutical formulation may provide symptomatic relief in individuals experiencing chronic gastrointestinal symptoms, particularly when such symptoms overlap with those commonly observed in mild forms of irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) and inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). As illustrated in Table 1, these symptoms such as bloating, abdominal discomfort, and altered bowel habits has demonstrated that the formulation's favourable tolerability profile and was associated with statistically and clinically meaningful improvements in patient-reported symptom scores. These improvements were most pronounced in participants with mild-to-moderate symptom severity at baseline, suggesting a potential role for the formulation as an adjunctive option for symptom management in functional and low-grade inflammatory gastrointestinal disorders.

DISCUSSION

The manuscript explains the potential therapeutic role of a novel nutraceutical formulation comprising of *Curcuma long* extract, *Piper nigrum* extract and *Cocos nucifera* oil in modulating the gastrointestinal inflammation and as a preventive measure in case of chronic inflammation induced colorectal cancer (CRC)

risk. The rationale for this combination was grounded in the well-established links between chronic inflammation, oxidative stress, mucosal disintegration, gut microbial dysbiosis and gastrointestinal malignancy, particularly in the context of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) during earlier stages.^[1,2,3] In IBD, persistent activation of inflammatory, including NF- κ B and STAT3, promotes the release of cytokines such as IL-6, IL-17, and IL-23, which in turn exacerbates mucosal injury, impair epithelial repair, and contribute to carcinogenic progression.^[5,7] The nutraceutical formulated targets these critical pathways through complementary mechanisms. Curcumin, the principal active compound in *Curcuma longa*, exhibits broad-spectrum anti-inflammatory effects, largely mediated through NF- κ B inhibition and suppression of COX-2 expression.^[44,45] The addition of *Piper nigrum* extract that contains the bioactive compound piperine enhances curcumin's bioavailability and offers independent anti-inflammatory benefits, notably through downregulation of TLR-4 mediated signalling and attenuation of oxidative stress.^[54] *Cocos nucifera* oil, rich in medium chain fatty acids and lauric acid provides mucosal protective effects, potentially restoring epithelial architecture and reducing TNF- α -driven colitis.^[59,63] This multi-targeted approach

is consistent with previous evidence supporting combinational nutraceuticals in gastrointestinal disease management.^[56,57] The preliminary Phase I pilot data, through limited scope, indicated subjective improvements in dyspepsia, bloating, and bowel regularity in patients with IBS and mild IBD. These findings align with reports that curcumin supplementation can alleviate IBD symptoms and reduce markers of oxidative damage.^[43,47] The observed tolerability of the formulation suggests encouraging clinical outcomes. A total of 70% of participants demonstrated very good improvement defined as resolution of all four major symptoms while the remainder achieved moderate or mild benefit. No non-response or dropout was observed, supporting both tolerability and adherence. Rapid and sustained improvements were reported in epigastric pain, lower abdominal discomfort, bowel irregularities, constipation, and abdominal bloating, symptoms frequently associated with IBS and early-stage IBD. Age-stratified analyses revealed nuanced differences: younger participants (21–44 years) experienced faster resolution of abdominal pain by day 15, whereas older participants (45–60 years) showed slightly higher sustained improvements in bowel regularity and bloating. Such patterns may reflect a combination of physiological factors (e.g., Vata predominance in older adults) and lifestyle-related influences, including dietary regularity, lower occupational stress, and consistent routines that support digestive regulation. From an Ayurvedic perspective, the observed benefits align with the formulation's actions in *Deepana* (enhancing digestive fire), *Pachana* (aiding digestion), and *Vata–Kapha* balance, particularly in managing “Kroorakoshta” or hard bowel type. Mechanistically, the synergy between curcumin and piperine may hold particular relevance for preventing inflammation-driven carcinogenesis. Piperine's modulation of Wnt/ β -catenin signaling.^[55] complements curcumin's suppression of pro-oncogenic pathways, potentially interrupting the sequence from chronic colitis to CRC.^[8,20] The inclusion of *Cocos nucifera* oil adds a nutritional lipid matrix to enhance phytochemical absorption and confer intrinsic anti-inflammatory and microbiota-modulating effects.^[64]

Nevertheless, interpretation of these findings must be tempered by several limitations. The pilot study's small sample size, absence of a placebo control, reliance on patient-reported outcomes, and short intervention duration limit generalizability of results and preclude conclusions regarding long-term efficacy, particularly in CRC prevention or sustained IBD remission. Although the formulation was administered at a standardized dose consistent with existing guidelines, the combined preparation itself has not yet been rigorously evaluated. Further investigation through a larger randomized, double-blind clinical trials with clearly defined dosing protocols is warranted to substantiate both efficacy and safety across broader populations. Future research should incorporate objective endpoints such as inflammatory

biomarkers (e.g., fecal calprotectin, CRP), colonoscopic scoring, and microbiome profiling. Given the genetic influences on IBD pathogenesis, including NOD2 variants in Crohn's disease.^[31] and DNA mismatch repair gene mutations in ulcerative colitis.^[6] integration of nutrigenomics could refine patient selection and identify likely responders. Moreover, as the formulation was selected based on its anticipated positive effects on the gut microbiota, dedicated studies are now warranted to elucidate its precise role in modulating microbial ecology within the broader context of diet–microbiome–gene interactions. In conclusion, this integrative approach leverages the anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and mucosal-protective properties of *Curcuma longa*, *Piper nigrum*, and *Cocos nucifera*. Preliminary real-world evidence indicates the combination is safe, well-tolerated, and may provide symptomatic relief in functional and low-grade inflammatory gastrointestinal disorders, with potential implications for CRC prevention. Rigorous clinical trials are now essential to confirm efficacy, optimize dosing, and assess long-term benefits.

CONCLUSION

The *Curcuma longa*, *Piper nigrum*, and *Cocos nucifera* formulation presents a mechanistically rational, multi-targeted approach to mitigating gastrointestinal inflammation, restoring mucosal integrity, and potentially reducing colorectal cancer risk in individuals with chronic low-grade inflammation. Phase I pilot data suggest favourable tolerability, high adherence, and notable symptom resolution across irritable bowel syndrome and mild inflammatory bowel disease cases. Although larger controlled studies have not yet been conducted, the nutraceutical formulation has been commercially available, with extensive anecdotal reports of clinical benefit and corroborative findings from clinicians' colonoscopic follow-ups. Despite these encouraging observations, the absence of placebo control, small sample size, and short intervention duration in the pilot necessitate cautious interpretation. Future large-scale, double-blind clinical trials incorporating objective biomarkers, colonoscopic scoring, microbiome profiling, and nutrigenomic stratification are essential to confirm efficacy and elucidate its long-term preventive potential.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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Authors Contribution

G.S. Aathithiah and M. Arunothayam have assisted in the research and development of the product and its manufacturing. Niranjana Murali Mohan contributed to the writing and initial preparation of the manuscript. G.S. Aathithiah and M. Arunothayam were responsible for revising and finalizing the manuscript.

REFERENCE

- Mattar, M. C., Lough, D., Pishvaian, M. J., & Charabaty, A. (2011). Current management of inflammatory bowel disease and colorectal cancer. *Gastrointestinal cancer research: GCR*, 4(2): 53.
- Lee, S. H., eun Kwon, J., & Cho, M. L. (2018). Immunological pathogenesis of inflammatory bowel disease. *Intestinal research*, 16(1): 26.
- Klampfer, L. (2011). Cytokines, inflammation and colon cancer. *Current cancer drug targets*, 11(4): 451-464.
- Rubin, D. C., Shaker, A., & Levin, M. S. (2012). Chronic intestinal inflammation: inflammatory bowel disease and colitis-associated colon cancer. *Frontiers in immunology*, 3: 107.
- Du, L., & Ha, C. (2020). Epidemiology and pathogenesis of ulcerative colitis. *Gastroenterology Clinics*, 49(4): 643-654.
- Mäki-Nevala, S., Ukwattage, S., Olkinuora, A., Almus, H., Ahtiainen, M., Ristimäki, A., ... & Peltomäki, P. (2021). Somatic mutation profiles as molecular classifiers of ulcerative colitis-associated colorectal cancer. *International Journal of Cancer*, 148(12): 2997-3007.
- Li, Y. I., de Haar, C., Chen, M., Deuring, J., Gerrits, M. M., Smits, R., ... & van der Woude, C. J. (2010). Disease-related expression of the IL6/STAT3/SOCS3 signalling pathway in ulcerative colitis and ulcerative colitis-related carcinogenesis. *Gut*, 59(2): 227-235.
- Fantini, M. C., & Pallone, F. (2008). Cytokines: from gut inflammation to colorectal cancer. *Current drug targets*, 9(5): 375-380.
- Petagna, L., Antonelli, A., Ganini, C., Bellato, V., Campanelli, M., Divizia, A., ... & Sica, G. S. (2020). Pathophysiology of Crohn's disease inflammation and recurrence. *Biology direct*, 15(1): 23.
- Cobrin, G. M., & Abreu, M. T. (2005). Defects in mucosal immunity leading to Crohn's disease. *Immunological reviews*, 206(1): 277-295.
- Wang, X., Yuan, W., Yang, C., Wang, Z., Zhang, J., Xu, D., ... & Sun, W. (2024). Emerging role of gut microbiota in autoimmune diseases. *Frontiers in immunology*, 15: 1365554.
- Algahtani, F. H., Farag, Y. M., Aljebreen, A. M., Alazzam, N. A., Aleem, A. S., Jabri, F. F., ... & Shoukri, M. M. (2016). Thromboembolic events in patients with inflammatory bowel disease. *Saudi Journal of Gastroenterology*, 22(6): 423-427.
- Alkhatami, M., Alshehri, F., & Nasiri, A. M. (2021). Thrombotic storm in inflammatory bowel disease: A case report. *Medicine: Case Reports and Study Protocols*, 2(5): e0081.
- Lakatos, L., Mester, G., Erdelyi, Z., David, G., Pandur, T., Balogh, M., ... & Lakatos, P. L. (2006). Risk factors for ulcerative colitis-associated colorectal cancer in a Hungarian cohort of patients with ulcerative colitis: results of a population-based study. *Inflammatory bowel diseases*, 12(3): 205-211.
- Tufano, A., Testa, A., Patturelli, M., Rispo, A., Fotticchia, V., Rufolo, P., ... & Castiglione, F. (2025). Venous and arterial thromboembolism in out-patients with inflammatory bowel disease: a single center study. *Thrombosis Update*, 100212.
- Lehoczki, A., Csípő, T., Lipécz, Á., Major, D., Fazekas-Pongor, V., Csík, B., ... & Fekete, M. (2025). Western Diet and Cognitive Decline: A Hungarian Perspective—Implications for the Design of the Semmelweis Study. *Nutrients*, 17(15): 2446.
- Giovannucci, E., Rimm, E. B., Stampfer, M. J., Colditz, G. A., Ascherio, A., & Willett, W. C. (1994). Intake of fat, meat, and fiber in relation to risk of colon cancer in men. *Cancer research*, 54(9): 2390-2397.
- Berkowitz, L., Schultz, B. M., Salazar, G. A., Pardo-Roa, C., Sebastián, V. P., Álvarez-Lobos, M. M., & Bueno, S. M. (2018). Impact of cigarette smoking on the gastrointestinal tract inflammation: opposing effects in Crohn's disease and ulcerative colitis. *Frontiers in immunology*, 9: 74.
- Mauliasari, I. R., Lee, H. J., Koo, S. Y., Hitayezu, E., Kieu, A. N. T., Lee, S. M., & Cha, K. H. (2024). Benzo (a) pyrene and Gut Microbiome Crosstalk: Health Risk Implications. *Toxics*, 12(12): 938.
- Hammerling, U., Bergman Laurila, J., Grafström, R., & Ilbäck, N. G. (2016). Consumption of red/processed meat and colorectal carcinoma: possible mechanisms underlying the significant association. *Critical reviews in food science and nutrition*, 56(4): 614-634.
- Hechenbleikner, E. M., & McQuade, J. A. (2015). Parasitic colitis. *Clinics in colon and rectal surgery*, 28(02): 079-086.
- Braseth, A. L., Elliott, D. E., & Ince, M. N. (2021). Parasitic infections of the gastrointestinal track and liver. *Gastroenterology Clinics of North America*, 50(2): 361.
- Cappelier, J. M. (2022). Bacterial and parasitic hazards and consumption of meat. *Hazard. Food Process. Distrib. Chain*, 1.
- Abdel Hamed, E. F., Mostafa, N. E., Farag, S. M., Ibrahim, M. N., Ibrahim, B. H., Rashed, H. E., ... & Fawzy, E. M. (2023). Human protozoa infection and dysplasia in ulcerative colitis: a neglected aspect in a prominent disease. *Parasitology Research*, 122(11): 2709-2718.
- Andreu-Ballester, J. C., Garcia-Ballesteros, C., Amigo, V., Ballester, F., Gil-Borras, R., Catalan-Serra, I., ... & Cuellar, C. (2013). Microsporidia and its relation to Crohn's disease. A retrospective study. *PloS one*, 8(4): e62107.

26. Mohammadi, R., Hosseini-Safa, A., Ardakani, M. J. E., & Rostami-Nejad, M. (2015). The relationship between intestinal parasites and some immune-mediated intestinal conditions. *Gastroenterology and hepatology from bed to bench*, 8(2): 123.
27. Ali, G. B., Muslim, O. T., & Abbas, A. G. (2019). Immune Modulation as A Result of Helminthes Infestation in Patients with Idiopathic Inflammatory Disease, Crohn's Disease and Ulcerative Colitis: Cases Control Study. *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology*, 13(4): 939-945.
28. Abdelmaksoud, H., Aboushousha, T., & El-Ashkar, A. (2022). Efficacy of coconut oil as therapeutic agent with potential anticancer activity in immunosuppressed mice with cryptosporidiosis: Parasitological, histopathological and immunohistochemical studies. *Parasitologists United Journal*, 15(1): 45-52.
29. Feil, R. (2006). Environmental and nutritional effects on the epigenetic regulation of genes. *Mutation Research/Fundamental and Molecular Mechanisms of Mutagenesis*, 600(1-2): 46-57.
30. Martínez-Maqueda, D., Miralles, B., & Recio, I. (2015). HT29 cell line. The Impact of Food Bioactives on Health: in vitro and ex vivo models, 113-124.
31. Heliö, T., Halme, L., Lappalainen, M., Fodstad, H., Paavola-Sakki, P., Turunen, U., ... & Kontula, K. (2003). CARD15/NOD2 gene variants are associated with familiarly occurring and complicated forms of Crohn's disease. *Gut*, 52(4): 558-562.
32. Vetrano, S., Borroni, E. M., Sarukhan, A., Savino, B., Bonecchi, R., Correale, C., ... & Danese, S. (2010). The lymphatic system controls intestinal inflammation and inflammation-associated colon cancer through the chemokine decoy receptor D6. *Gut*, 59(2): 197-206.
33. German, S., Aslam, H. M., Saleem, S., Raees, A., Anum, T., Alvi, A. A., & Haseeb, A. (2013). Carcinogenesis of PIK3CA. *Hereditary cancer in clinical practice*, 11(1): 5.
34. El Asri, A., Zarrouq, B., El Kinany, K., Bouguenouch, L., Ouldin, K., & El Rhazi, K. (2020). Associations between nutritional factors and KRAS mutations in colorectal cancer: a systematic review. *BMC cancer*, 20(1): 696.
35. Gurjao, C., Zhong, R., Haruki, K., Li, Y. Y., Spurr, L. F., Lee-Six, H., ... & Giannakis, M. (2021). Discovery and features of an alkylating signature in colorectal cancer. *Cancer discovery*, 11(10): 2446-2455.
36. Government of India. (2001). *Curcuma longa* (Vol. 1, pp. 77-79). In *The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India*. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Department of AYUSH.
37. Hewlings, S. J., & Kalman, D. S. (2017). Curcumin: A review of its effects on human health. *Foods*, 6(10): 92.
38. Rapti, E., Adamantidi, T., Efthymiopoulos, P., Kyzas, G. Z., & Tsoupras, A. (2024). Potential applications of the anti-inflammatory, antithrombotic and antioxidant health-promoting properties of curcumin: A critical review. *Nutraceuticals*, 4(4): 562-595.
39. Shahiduzzaman, M. D., & Dauschies, A. (2011). Curcumin: a natural herb extract with antiparasitic properties. *Nature Helps... How Plants and Other Organisms Contribute to Solve Health Problems*, 141-152.
40. Shanmugam, M. K., Rane, G., Kanchi, M. M., Arfuso, F., Chinnathambi, A., Zayed, M. E., ... & Sethi, G. (2015). The multifaceted role of curcumin in cancer prevention and treatment. *Molecules*, 20(2): 2728-2769.
41. Hussein, A., Rashed, S., El Hayawan, I., El-Sayed, R., & Ali, H. (2017). Evaluation of the anti-schistosomal effects of turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) versus praziquantel in *Schistosoma mansoni* infected mice. *Iranian journal of parasitology*, 12(4): 587.
42. Sadeghi, M., Dehnavi, S., Asadirad, A., Xu, S., Majeed, M., Jamialahmadi, T., ... & Sahebkar, A. (2023). Curcumin and chemokines: mechanism of action and therapeutic potential in inflammatory diseases. *Inflammopharmacology*, 31(3): 1069-1093.
43. Bastaki, S. M., Al Ahmed, M. M., Al Zaabi, A., Amir, N., & Adeghate, E. (2016). Effect of turmeric on colon histology, body weight, ulcer, IL-23, MPO and glutathione in acetic-acid-induced inflammatory bowel disease in rats. *BMC complementary and alternative medicine*, 16(1): 72.
44. Goel, A., Boland, C. R., & Chauhan, D. P. (2001). Specific inhibition of cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) expression by dietary curcumin in HT-29 human colon cancer cells. *Cancer letters*, 172(2): 111-118.
45. Zoi, V., Galani, V., Lianos, G. D., Voulgaris, S., Kyritsis, A. P., & Alexiou, G. A. (2021). The role of curcumin in cancer treatment. *Biomedicines*, 9(9): 1086.
46. Tabeshpour, J., Hashemzaei, M., & Sahebkar, A. (2018). The regulatory role of curcumin on platelet functions. *Journal of cellular biochemistry*, 119(11): 8713-8722.
47. Peterson, C. T., Vaughn, A. R., Sharma, V., Chopra, D., Mills, P. J., Peterson, S. N., & Sivamani, R. K. (2018). Effects of turmeric and curcumin dietary supplementation on human gut microbiota: A double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled pilot study.
48. Zhu, J., & He, L. (2024). The modulatory effects of curcumin on the gut microbiota: A potential strategy for disease treatment and health promotion. *Microorganisms*, 12(4): 642.
49. Government of India. (2001). *Piper nigrum* (Vol. 3, pp. 172-175). In *The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India*. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Department of AYUSH.
50. Mehmood, M. H., & Gilani, A. H. (2010). Pharmacological basis for the medicinal use of black pepper and piperine in gastrointestinal disorders. *Journal of medicinal food*, 13(5): 1086-1096.

51. Ablon, G. (2021). Nutraceuticals. *Dermatologic clinics*, 39(3): 417-427.
52. Sarkar, M., & Chawla, P. (2022). Therapeutic Efficacy of Black Pepper in Gastrointestinal Disorders. In *Herbs, Spices, and Medicinal Plants for Human Gastrointestinal Disorders* (pp. 105-124). Apple Academic Press.
53. Hu, Y., Wang, Y., Gao, H., Yang, G., Xie, J., He, Z., ... & Hu, W. (2025). Piperine Improves DSS- Induced Colitis in Mice via Inhibition of Inflammation and Modulation of Gut Microbiota. *Phytotherapy Research*.
54. Gupta, R. A., Motiwala, M. N., Dumore, N. G., Danao, K. R., & Ganjare, A. B. (2015). Effect of piperine on inhibition of FFA induced TLR4 mediated inflammation and amelioration of acetic acid induced ulcerative colitis in mice. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 164: 239-246.
55. de Almeida, G. C., Oliveira, L. F., Predes, D., Fokoue, H. H., Kuster, R. M., Oliveira, F. L., ... & Abreu, J. G. (2020). Piperine suppresses the Wnt/ β -catenin pathway and has anti-cancer effects on colorectal cancer cells. *Scientific reports*, 10(1): 11681.
56. Li, Q., Zhai, W., Jiang, Q., Huang, R., Liu, L., Dai, J., ... & Wu, Q. (2015). Curcumin– piperine mixtures in self-microemulsifying drug delivery system for ulcerative colitis therapy. *International journal of pharmaceuticals*, 490(1-2): 22-31.
57. Yüksel, B., Hızlı Deniz, A. A., Şahin, F., Sahin, K., & Türkel, N. (2023). Cannabinoid compounds in combination with curcumin and piperine display an anti-tumorigenic effect against colon cancer cells. *Frontiers in pharmacology*, 14: 1145666.
58. Martins, A. S. D. P., Araújo, O. R. P. D., Gomes, A. D. S., Araujo, F. L. C., Oliveira Junior, J., Vasconcelos, J. K. G. D., ... & Moura, F. A. (2024). Effect of Curcumin plus Piperine on redox imbalance, fecal calprotectin and cytokine levels in inflammatory bowel disease patients: A randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled clinical trial. *Pharmaceuticals*, 17(7): 849.
59. Alok, P. C. (2013). Effect of Coconut Oil on Ulcerative Colitis in the Mouse Model.
60. Government of India. (2001). *Cocus nucifera* (Vol. 3, pp. 198-200). In *The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India*. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Department of AYUSH.
61. Deen, A., Visvanathan, R., Wickramarachchi, D., Marikkar, N., Nammi, S., Jayawardana, B. C., & Liyanage, R. (2021). Chemical composition and health benefits of coconut oil: an overview. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 101(6): 2182-2193.
62. Reddy, B. S. (1992). Dietary fat and colon cancer: animal model studies. *Lipids*, 27(10): 807-813.
63. Zundler, S., Dietz, L., Matzel, K. E., Geppert, C. I., Becker, E., Rath, T., ... & Atreya, R. (2018). Successful long-term treatment of diversion colitis with topical coconut oil application. *Official journal of the American College of Gastroenterology| ACG*, 113(12): 1908-1910.
64. Patrone, V., Minuti, A., Lizier, M., Miragoli, F., Lucchini, F., Trevisi, E., ... & Callegari, M. L. (2018). Differential effects of coconut versus soy oil on gut microbiota composition and predicted metabolic function in adult mice. *BMC genomics*, 19(1): 808.